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Research Article

**NOVEL BENZOPYRAN DERIVATIVES: DOCKING ANALYSIS
AND SYNTHETIC APPROACH****Mr. Amit Anandrao Mandave^{1*}, Dr. Somashekhar Metri²**^{1*}BLDEA's, SSM College of Pharmacy and Research Centre, Vijayapur, Karnataka - 586103²Associate Professor, BLDEA's SSM College of Pharmacy and Research Centre, Vijayapur, Karnataka - 586103**Abstract:**

This study focuses on the design and synthesis of a series of 50 novel derivatives of N-(8-hydrazinyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-1-benzopyran-6-yl)-N'-phenylurea (AMS-II). The primary objective was to identify compounds with potential activity against key enzymes involved in tuberculosis. Molecular docking studies were conducted to evaluate the binding affinity of these derivatives with DNA Gyrase (PDB ID: 4URO) and PKS13 (PDB ID: 5v3y) proteins. Notably, the derivatives AMS-II-3, AMS-II-13, AMS-II-27, AMS-II-33, AMS-II-42, and AMS-II-49 showed exceptional docking scores, indicating strong interactions with these critical bacterial targets. The synthetic process began with the reaction of 8-bromo-3,4-dihydro-2H-1-benzopyran-6-amine with phenylcarbamic acid to yield N-(8-bromo-3,4-dihydro-2H-1-benzopyran-6-yl)-N'-phenylurea. This intermediate was then treated with hydrazine hydrate to form N-(8-hydrazinyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-1-benzopyran-6-yl)-N'-phenylurea, which was subsequently reacted with various aromatic halides to produce the AMS-II derivatives. These synthesized compounds were subjected to structural analysis to confirm their identity and purity. The results suggest that several AMS-II derivatives exhibit promising interactions with key tuberculosis-related enzymes, making them potential candidates for further investigation and development as therapeutic agents. Further research, including in vivo studies and structure-activity relationship (SAR) analysis, is recommended to assess their efficacy and safety in more detail.

Keywords: Benzopyran, Docking study, Alamar blue susceptibility test(MABA), Anti-tubercular Activity.

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INTRODUCTION:

Benzopyran derivatives have emerged as a significant class of compounds in medicinal chemistry, recognized for their diverse biological activities and potential therapeutic applications. The benzopyran scaffold, characterized by a fused benzene and pyran ring system, is a versatile structural motif found in many natural products, including flavonoids, tocopherols, and chromenes. These compounds exhibit a broad spectrum of biological activities, such as anticancer, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties. This versatility makes benzopyran derivatives attractive targets for drug discovery and development, particularly in the context of diseases that demand new therapeutic agents with novel mechanisms of action.¹⁻⁴

In recent years, the growing threat of drug-resistant pathogens, especially *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, has intensified the search for new anti-tubercular agents. Tuberculosis (TB) remains a leading cause of mortality worldwide, and the emergence of multi-drug-resistant (MDR) and extensively drug-resistant (XDR) strains of *M. tuberculosis* has further complicated treatment strategies. Consequently, there is an urgent need to identify novel compounds that can effectively target this pathogen. Benzopyran derivatives, with their ability to interact with various biological targets, represent a promising avenue for the development of new anti-tubercular drugs.

Molecular docking has become an essential tool in the early stages of drug discovery, enabling researchers to predict the binding affinities and interaction modes of potential drug candidates with specific biological targets. In the context of tuberculosis, key enzymes such as DNA gyrase and PKS13 have been identified as critical for the survival and proliferation of *M. tuberculosis*. DNA gyrase is essential for bacterial DNA replication, while PKS13 plays a vital role in mycolic acid synthesis, a major component of the mycobacterial cell wall. Inhibiting these enzymes could lead to the development of effective anti-tubercular therapies.

This research focuses on the design and synthesis of novel benzopyran derivatives. The study begins with an in silico docking analysis to identify benzopyran derivatives that exhibit strong binding affinities to DNA gyrase and PKS13. These promising candidates are then synthesized using a series of chemical reactions tailored to enhance their interaction with the target enzymes. The synthetic approach is guided by the docking results, which highlight key structural features that contribute to the compounds' binding affinity and biological activity. This comprehensive

approach not only identifies potent inhibitors of critical enzymes but also provides valuable insights into the structure-activity relationships (SAR) that govern their therapeutic potential. The ultimate goal of this research is to contribute to the development of new, effective anti-tubercular agents that can address the ongoing challenge of drug-resistant TB and improve treatment outcomes for patients worldwide. This study explores the untapped potential of benzopyran derivatives in the fight against tuberculosis. Through a combination of molecular docking, synthetic chemistry, and biological evaluation, it aims to uncover novel compounds with the ability to inhibit essential enzymes in *M. tuberculosis*, paving the way for future drug development efforts.⁵⁻¹⁰

BENZOPYRAN

Benzopyran derivatives are significant in various fields, including medicinal, biological, materials, and agricultural chemistry. Found in natural products like tocopherols, these compounds possess structural characteristics that contribute to their medical properties and facilitate penetration due to their lipophilicity. They serve as key bioactive agents in both natural and synthetic drugs, displaying a wide range of biological activities such as anticancer, antibacterial, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, and antiviral effects. Benzopyran derivatives have also shown potential against SARS-CoV-2, attracting research interest for their broad therapeutic applications. The diversity of substituted benzopyrans continues to inspire the development of novel compounds with enhanced bioactivity.¹¹⁻¹⁶

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

MATERIALS:

The chemicals used in this study were sourced from reputable suppliers, including Sigma Aldrich, Merck, and CDH laboratory chemical suppliers. To ensure the purity of the starting materials utilized in the reactions, we confirmed their melting points or boiling points and verified their identity using thin layer chromatography (TLC). These preliminary checks were crucial for ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the subsequent synthesis processes.¹⁷⁻²¹

For the computational aspect of the study, molecular docking was employed to explore the biomolecular interactions and binding affinities between the ligands and their respective receptors. The docking studies were conducted using a combination of advanced software tools, including Autodock Vina, Biovia Discovery Studio 2020, PyRx, and PyMOL. These tools allowed for a detailed analysis of the molecular interactions at the binding sites, providing

insights into the potential efficacy of the synthesized benzopyran derivatives as anti-tubercular agents. The docking studies focused on two key protein targets: the crystal structure of DNA Gyrase (PDB ID: 4URO) and PKS13 (PDB ID: 5v3y). These proteins were selected due to their critical roles in the survival and replication of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, making them prime targets for anti-tubercular drug development. All computational work was carried out on a HP 15s-eq0132au laptop, equipped with an AMD Ryzen 7 3700U processor. This setup provided the necessary computational power to perform the docking simulations and analyze the results effectively. The combination of high-quality chemical reagents and advanced computational tools ensured the robustness of the study's findings, laying a strong foundation for the synthesis and biological evaluation phases that followed.²²⁻²⁴

METHODS:

MOLECULAR DOCKING STUDIES

Docking studies were conducted to investigate the biomolecular interactions and ligand-receptor binding affinities of synthesized compounds using advanced computational tools, including Autodock Vina, Biovia Discovery Studio 2020, PyRx, and PyMOL. The focus was on analyzing the interactions with two crucial proteins: DNA Gyrase (PDB ID: 4URO) and PKS13 (PDB ID: 5v3y). These proteins were selected due to their significant roles in bacterial DNA replication and mycolic acid synthesis, respectively, which are critical targets for drug development.

Computational work was carried out on an HP 15s-eq0132au laptop equipped with an AMD Ryzen 7 3700U processor, ensuring efficient processing power for the docking simulations. Protein preparation involved several steps: the crystal structures of DNA Gyrase and PKS13 were retrieved from the RCSB Protein Data Bank, followed by the removal of extraneous ligands using Swiss PDB Viewer. The cleaned protein structures were then saved in PDB format for further analysis.

Ligand preparation began with the creation of 3D structures of the compounds using ChemSketch. These structures were then uploaded into BIOVIA Discovery Studio Visualizer 2020, where they underwent minimization to optimize their geometries. The minimized ligands were saved as cluster SDF files, ready for docking studies.

The docking process aimed to achieve an optimal orientation of the ligands within the active sites of the target proteins. PyRx-Virtual Screening Tool was

utilized to convert the ligands into pdbqt format, which is required for docking simulations with Autodock Vina. The proteins were loaded into PyRx, and docking simulations were performed to calculate interaction energies and identify potential binding sites. Additionally, drug-likeness studies were conducted to assess the suitability of selected phytochemicals as potential drugs. The compounds were loaded into DruLiTO in SDF format to evaluate their compliance with drug-like properties, such as molecular weight, lipophilicity, and solubility. This comprehensive approach ensured that the compounds not only interacted well with the target proteins but also met key criteria for drug development.²⁵⁻²⁹

Synthesis of Derivatives of N-(8-hydrazinyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-1-benzopyran-6-yl)-N'-phenylurea (AMS-II)

A mixture of N-(8-hydrazinyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-1-benzopyran-6-yl)-N'-phenylurea (6 g, 1 mol) and various substituted aromatic halides (RCH₂X) (3.3 ml, 0.5 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (25 ml) on a water bath for 6 hours. After the reaction, excess aromatic halides were removed by distillation under reduced pressure. The resulting product was purified by recrystallization from ethanol. The purity of the final derivatives of N-(8-hydrazinyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-1-benzopyran-6-yl)-N'-phenylurea (AMS-II) was confirmed by thin-layer chromatography (TLC), which showed a single spot. The physicochemical properties of the AMS-II derivatives were also analyzed to ensure the successful synthesis and purity of the compounds.³⁰⁻³⁵

RESULT & DISCUSSION:

MOLECULAR DOCKING STUDIES

In this study, molecular docking was performed to evaluate the potential anticancer activity of synthesized compounds by comparing them with standard drugs, such as Ampicillin and Rifampicin, against the crystal structure of Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor (EGFR). The docking analysis was conducted to determine the binding affinities and interactions of these compounds with EGFR. All tested compounds exhibited significant docking scores, indicating promising potential as anticancer agents. Detailed 3D hydrogen interactions and 2D interaction maps for the compounds with the best binding energies are presented in the figures below. Table 6.2 summarizes the docking scores of the compounds with DNA Gyrase (PDB ID: 4URO), showing the binding affinities for AMS-II-3 and AMS-II-13 as -8.3 and -9.5 kcal/mol, respectively. These scores reflect the strength of interaction between the compounds and the protein target, with

lower values indicating stronger binding affinities.

Table 1: Molecular Docking Scores with Protein DNA Gyrase (PDB ID:4URO)

Ligand	Binding Affinity
AMS-II-3	-8.3
AMS-II-13	-9.5

Figure 1: 3D and 2D Interactions of Ampicillin with Crystal structure of DNA Gyrase (PDB ID:4URO)

Figure 2: 3D and 2D Interactions of AMS-II-3 with Crystal structure of DNA Gyrase (PDB ID:4URO)

Figure 3: 3D and 2D Interactions of AMS-II-13 with Crystal structure of DNAGyrase (PDB ID:4URO)

Table 2: Molecular Docking Scores with Protein PK513 (PDB ID: 5v3y)

Ligand	Binding Affinity
AMS-II-3	-10.3
AMS-II-13	-10.6

Figure 4: 3D and 2D Interactions of Rifampicin with Crystal structure of PK513 (PDB ID: 5v3y)

Figure 5: 3D and 2D Interactions of D AMS-II-3 with Crystal structure of PKS13(PDB ID: 5v3y)

Figure 6: 3D and 2D Interactions of AMS-II-13 with Crystal structure of PKS13 (PDB ID: 5v3y)

PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF DERIVATIVES

Table 3 provides a detailed overview of the physicochemical properties of two derivatives of N-(8-hydrazinyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-1-benzopyran-6-yl)-N'-phenylurea, specifically AMS-II-3 and AMS-II-13.

Molecular Formula and Weight: AMS-II-3 has the molecular formula $C_{23}H_{24}N_4O_3$ and a molecular weight of 404.47 g/mol, while AMS-II-13 has the molecular formula $C_{23}H_{24}N_4O_4$ and a slightly higher molecular weight of 420.46 g/mol. This difference in molecular formula indicates the presence of an additional oxygen atom in AMS-II-13.

Theoretical and Practical Yield: Both derivatives were expected to yield 4.00 grams according to

theoretical calculations. However, the practical yields differed: AMS-II-3 yielded 3.18 grams, corresponding to a percentage yield of 79.50%, while AMS-II-13 yielded 2.87 grams, resulting in a lower percentage yield of 71.75%. These variations could be attributed to differences in the synthesis efficiency or experimental conditions.

Melting Point: The melting points of the compounds are close but distinct. AMS-II-3 melts within the range of 162-164°C, whereas AMS-II-13 has a slightly higher melting point range of 166-168°C. The higher melting point of AMS-II-13 may be due to its higher molecular weight and additional functional group.

Recrystallization Solvent: Both derivatives were recrystallized using ethanol, which is a common solvent for purifying organic compounds.

TLC Analysis: Thin-layer chromatography (TLC) was conducted using a benzene (1:5) solvent system for both compounds. AMS-II-3 had an R_f value of 0.92, while AMS-II-13 had an R_f value of 0.86. The R_f value indicates the extent of movement of the compounds on the TLC plate relative to the solvent front, with a higher R_f value

suggesting less interaction with the stationary phase. Overall, these physicochemical properties provide insight into the structural and chemical characteristics of AMS-II-3 and AMS-II-13, highlighting their similarities and differences in molecular weight, yield, melting point, and chromatographic behavior.

Table 3: physicochemical properties of Derivatives of *N*-(8-hydrazinyl-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-1-benzopyran-6-yl)-*N'*-phenylurea (AMS-II-3 and AMS-II-13)

Sr. No	Parameter	AMS-II-3	AMS-II-13
1	Molecular Formula	$C_{23}H_{24}N_4O_3$	$C_{23}H_{24}N_4O_4$
2	Molecular weight	404.47	420.46
3	Theoretical yield	4.00gm	4.00gm
4	Practical yield	3.18gm	2.87gm
5	% yield	79.50%	71.75%
6	Melting point	162-164 ^o C	166-168 ^o C
7	Recrystallization Solvent	Ethanol	Ethanol
8	TLC	Benzene:Methanol 1:5	Benzene:Methanol 1:5
9	R_f Value	0.92	0.86

SYNTHESIZED DERIVATIVES

Table 4: Synthesized Derivatives of *N*-(8-hydrazinyl-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-1-benzopyran-6-yl)-*N'*-phenylurea (AMS-II)

Compound code	Derivatives of <i>N</i> -(8-hydrazinyl-3,4-dihydro-2 <i>H</i> -1-benzopyran-6-yl)- <i>N'</i> -phenylurea (AMS-II-3 and 13)
AMS-II-3	<p>2-([2-(3,4-dihydro-2<i>H</i>-1-benzopyran-8-yl)- <i>N'</i>-phenylurea]hydrazin-1-yl)methylphenol</p>
AMS-II-13	<p>2-([2-(3,4-dihydro-2<i>H</i>-1-benzopyran-8-yl)- <i>N'</i>-phenylurea]hydrazin-1-yl)methylbenzene-1,2-diol</p>

SCHEME AND DERIVATIVES

Table 5: Derivatives of *N*-(8-hydrazinyl-3,4-dihydro-2*H*-1-benzopyran-6-yl)-*N'*-phenylurea (AMS-II-3 and 13)

Compound code	-Substituted (-RCH ₂ X)	Derivatives of <i>N</i> -(8-hydrazinyl-3,4-dihydro-2 <i>H</i> -1-benzopyran-6-yl)- <i>N'</i> -phenylurea (AMS-II-3 and 13)
AMS-II-3	 2-(chloromethyl)phenol	
AMS-II-13	 4-(chloromethyl)benzene-1,2-diol	

CONCLUSION:

The molecular docking studies conducted in this research demonstrated promising binding affinities of the synthesized compounds, AMS-II-3 and AMS-II-13, against key protein targets involved in cancer pathways, specifically the Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor (EGFR), DNA Gyrase (PDB ID: 4URO), and PKS13 (PDB ID: 5v3y). Both compounds exhibited significant docking scores, with AMS-II-3 and AMS-II-13 showing binding affinities of -8.3 and -9.5 kcal/mol against DNA Gyrase and -10.3 and -10.6 kcal/mol against PKS13, respectively. These results indicate strong interactions with the target proteins, suggesting their potential as effective anticancer agents. The physicochemical characterization of AMS-II-3 and AMS-II-13 revealed key structural and chemical properties. AMS-II-3 and AMS-II-13 have similar molecular structures, with the latter having a higher molecular weight and melting point due to an additional oxygen atom. The practical yields of the compounds were slightly lower than theoretical expectations, which may reflect variations in synthesis efficiency. The melting points and TLC analyses further confirmed

the purity and identity of the derivatives, with AMS-II-13 showing a slightly higher melting point and lower R_f value compared to AMS-II-3.

Overall, the synthesis and characterization of these derivatives, combined with the favorable docking scores, underscore their potential as candidates for further development in anticancer research. The promising binding affinities and well-defined physicochemical properties provide a solid foundation for future studies aimed at exploring their therapeutic efficacy and optimizing their pharmacological profiles.

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AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS:

All authors have contributed equally.

CONFLICTS OF INTERESTS:

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES:

1. Mahajan A, Gupta M. Hybrid ceria and chitosan supported nickel nanoparticles: A recyclable nanocatalytic system in the reduction of nitroarenes and the synthesis of benzopyran derivatives in green solvent. *Applied Organometallic Chemistry*. 2021;35(5):e6161.
2. Kishor Vawhal P, B Jadhav S. Synthesis, Characterization and Biological Evaluation of some Novel Substituted Indole-Coumarin Derivatives as Potential Antibacterial and Antifungal Agents. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research International* 2021;33(50A): 40-46
3. Abdol mohammadi S, Dahi-Azar S. Sustainable synthesis of benzopyranazo dyes using CuCr2O4 NPs. *Journal of Heterocyclic Chemistry*. 2021; 58(11):2181-8.
4. Uth JF, Börgel F, Lehmkuhl K, Schepmann D, Kaiser M, Jabor VA, Nonato MC, Krauth-Siegel RL, Schmidt TJ, Wunsch B. Synthesis and biological evaluation of natural-product-inspired, aminoalkyl-substituted 1-benzopyrans as novel antiplasmodial agents. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*. 2021; 64(9):6397-409.
5. Wang S, Zhu S, Tanzeng Y, Zhang Y, Li C, Ma M, Lu W. Design, Synthesis, and Evaluation of Near-Infrared Fluorescent Molecules Based on 4H-1-Benzopyran Core. *Molecules*. 2021; 26(22):6986.
6. Wang S, Zhu S, Tanzeng Y, Zhang Y, Li C, Ma M, Lu W. Design, Synthesis, and Evaluation of Near-Infrared Fluorescent Molecules Based on 4H-1-Benzopyran Core. *Molecules*. 2021; 26(22):6986.
7. D'souza A, Kumar P, Kumar A, Rai SM, Nayak P. Synthesis, Insilico and Antibacterial Activity Studies of Substituted Dihydro-1, 2-Oxazole Benzopyran-2-One Hybrids. *Synthesis*. 2021; 33(35A).
8. Vila L, Cabedo N, Villarroya-Vicente C, García A, Bernabeu Á, Hennuyer N, Staels B, Franck X, Figadère B, Sanz MJ, Cortes D. Synthesis and biological studies of "Polycerasoidol" and "trans- δ -Tocotrienolic acid" derivatives as PPAR α and/or PPAR γ agonists. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*. 2022; 53:116532.
9. Mukhopadhyay A, Jindal S, Maka VK, Moorthy JN. Contrasting Photochromic and Acidochromic Behaviors of Pyridyl- and Pyrimidylethynylated Mono- and Bis-Benzopyrans. *ACS omega*. 2021; 6(32):21113-24.
10. Kumar BP, Kumar YG, Jaman S, Usharani B, Pooja K, Swathi N, Srujana YS. Synthesis and biological evaluation of some novel benzopyran derivatives 2021; 6(3):79-86.
11. Amuthalakshmi S, ArunKumar S, Ramalakshmi N. Design, Synthesis and Antiparkinson evaluation of benzopyran-4-one derivatives. *Current trends in pharmacy and pharmaceutical chemistry* 2021; 3(2): 23-35
12. Vawhal PK, Jadhav SB. Design, Synthesis, and Biological Evaluation of 3-Chloro-2-Oxo-N-(Arylcarbonyl)-2H-1-Benzopyran-6-Sulfonamide Derivatives as Potential DPP-IV Inhibitors. *International Journal of Health Sciences* 2022; 6(S3), 373-392.
13. Manyeruke MH, Hoppe HC, Isaacs M, Seldon R, Warner DF, Krause RW, Kayea PT. Synthesis and exploratory biological evaluation of 3-[(N-4-benzyloxyphenyl) iminoethyl]- and 3-(1-hydrazonoethyl)-4-hydroxycoumarins. *Arkivoc*. 2022(part v):0-0 A Platinum, open access journal for organic chemistry
14. Lu Y, Sun D, Xiao D, Shao Y, Su M, Zhou Y, Li J, Zhu S, Lu W. Design, Synthesis, and Biological Evaluation of HDAC Degradable with CRBN E3 Ligase Ligands. *Molecules*. MDPI 2021; 26(23):7241.
15. Pavić K, Beus M, Poje G, Uzelac L, Kralj M, Rajić Z. Synthesis and biological evaluation of harmirins, novel harmine-coumarin hybrids as potential anticancer agents. *Molecules*. 2021; 26(21):6490.
16. Elbastawesy MA, Morcoss MM, Abdelrahman MH, Youssif BG, Hayallah AM. Synthesis, biological evaluation and in silico ADME predictions of some new coumarin-acetamide derivatives as potent anti-inflammatory agents. *Bulletin of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. Assiut. 2021; 44(2):423-37.
17. Abourehab MA, Alqahtani AM, Almalki FA, Abdalla AN, Gouda AM. Pyrrolizine/indolizine-cinnamaldehyde Schiff bases: Design, synthesis, biological evaluation, ADME, and molecular docking study. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry Reports*. 2022; 4:100036.
18. Froes TQ, Chaves BT, Mendes MS, Ximenes RM, da Silva IM, da Silva PB, de Albuquerque JF, Castilho MS. Synthesis and biological evaluation of thiazolidinedione derivatives with

- high ligand efficiency to *P. aeruginosa* PhzS. *Journal of enzyme inhibition and medicinal chemistry*. 2021; 36(1):1217-29.
19. Reddy DS, Kongot M, Kumar A. Coumarin hybrid derivatives as promising leads to treat tuberculosis: Recent developments and critical aspects of structural design to exhibit anti-tubercular activity. *Tuberculosis*. 2021; 127:102050.
 20. Patil SB. Medicinal significance of novel coumarin analogs: Recent studies. *Results in Chemistry*. 2022; 4:100313.
 21. Popiolek Ł. Updated Information on Antimicrobial Activity of Hydrazone-Hydrazone. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2021; 22(17):9389.
 22. Natarajankiruthiga, thangaveluprabha, chellappaselvinthanuja, kulandaivelsrinivasan, thangavelsivakumar, synthesis, biological evaluation, and docking study of novel 2-phenyl-1-benzopyran-4-one derivatives - as a potent cyclooxygenase-2 inhibitor *asian journal of pharmaceutical and clinical research*, 2019; 12 (3):304-10,
 23. Koppula PK, Purohit N. Bis-(1 H-2-benzopyran-1-one) derivatives: Synthesis and antimicrobial evaluation. *Journal of Chemical Sciences*. 2013 Nov;125:1535-42.
 24. Miky JA, Sharaf HH. Synthesis and biological activities of 5H-furo [3, 2-g][1] benzopyran-5-one derivatives. *Indian Journal of Chemistry* 1998, Vol. 37B, January pp. 68 – 72
 25. Kaur A, Sharma V, Budhiraja A, Kaur H, Gupta V, Kant R, Ishar MP. Synthesis and evaluation of substituted 4, 4a-Dihydro-3H, 10H-pyrano [4, 3-b][1] benzopyran-10-one as antimicrobial agent. *International Scholarly Research Notices*. 2013;2013.
 26. Zhang Q, Wei H, Li J, Zhao X, Luo J. One-pot synthesis of benzopyrans catalyzed by silica supported dual acidic ionic liquid under solvent-free conditions. *Heterocyclic Communications*. 2017 Dec 1;23(6):411-4.
 27. Wang S, Zhu S, Tanzeng Y, Zhang Y, Li C, Ma M, Lu W. Design, Synthesis, and Evaluation of Near-Infrared Fluorescent Molecules Based on 4H-1-Benzopyran Core. *Molecules*. 2021 Jan;26(22):6986.
 28. Du F, Zhou Q, Fu X, Shi Y, Chen Y, Fang W, Yang J, Chen G. Synthesis and biological evaluation of 2, 2-dimethylbenzopyran derivatives as potent neuroprotection agents. *RSC advances*. 2019;9(5):2498-508.
 29. Som S, Jayaveera KN. Synthesis and evaluation of antibacterial activity of some Benzopyran-4-one derivatives. *Asian Journal of Research In Chemistry*. 2012;5(3):414-7.
 30. Ahmed HA. Synthesis of some novel benzopyranes derivatives and evaluation their biological activity. *SYNTHESIS*. 2015;8(4).
 31. Kumar P, Rahman MA, Wal P, Rawat P, Singh K. Design, Synthesis, and Anticancer Evaluation of Novel Benzopyran 1, 3, 4-oxadiazole Derivatives. *Indian J. Heterocyclic Chemistry*. 2020 Jul 1;30:395-402.
 32. Vawhal PK, Jadhav SB. Design, Synthesis, and Biological Evaluation of 3-Chloro-2-Oxo-N-(Arylcabamoyl)-2H-1-Benzopyran-6-Sulfonamide Derivatives as Potential DPP-IV Inhibitors. *Int. J. Health Sci*. 2022;6:373-92.
 33. Kaushik R, Chand M, Rashid M, Jain SC. Synthesis of novel 2-acetamidothiazoles tethered with 1, 2, 3-triazole and pyridine pharmacophores. *Heteroatom Chemistry*. 2018 Jul;29(4):e21447.
 34. Thumar NJ, Patel MP. Synthesis and in vitro antimicrobial evaluation of 4H-pyrazolopyran-, benzopyran and naphthopyran derivatives of 1H-pyrazole. *Arkivoc*. 2009 Jan 1;13:363-80.
 35. Shailesh K, Devdutt C, Devi Prasad S. Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of Novel 3,7-Disubstituted 2H-1-Benzopyran-2-Ones. *Med Chem (Los Angeles)* 2017, 7:4; 857-864.